

The Benefits of a Silvopastoral Sheep System and the Supports Available in Ireland

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Sheep grazing in a recently established agroforestry site

References

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Sheep are well suited to agroforestry in Ireland, utilising dense grass and understory growth while benefiting from tree shade and shelter. Species like alder and willow provide protection from rain, while sheep improve soil fertility by cycling nutrients and controlling undesired sheep feed plants like bracken and gorse, reducing herbicide use. Silvopasture can contribute to facilitate the tree cover restoration in upland areas while maintaining grazing, reducing livestock stress, improving productivity, and enhancing water retention to prevent flooding if adequate protectors are used. Sheep grown by using silvopasture supports meat and wool production, boosting biodiversity and carbon sequestration while complying with environmental protections. Sheep grazing in silvopasture lands are adaptable, with cost-effective tree protection allowing flexible layouts. Trees can help improve lamb survival, enhance growth, and extend grazing by up to 17 weeks, therefore reducing feed winter costs. Tree dense clusters or contour bands work well, particularly in riparian zones where they improve water quality. Proper management is key, as setting up grazing on young tree plantations may damage trees. Rotational grazing is essential, and some trees may need long-term protection, with environment friendly bioplastic mesh guards proving effective, as seen in Loughgall, Co. Armagh. Silvopasture provides timber, fodder, and on-farm resources. Pruned trees yield high-value timber, while coppiced willow and hazel supply browsing can make up to 40% of a sheep's diet. Durable timber from larch, oak, and chestnut also reduces fencing costs. Coppiced wood can also be used as mulch or bedding, while orchard grazing improves soil fertility and reduces mowing costs, with Shropshire sheep being ideal. Silvopasture stabilizes soil, reduces erosion, and improves water retention. Ireland's Agroforestry Scheme (FT8) requires a minimum of 400 trees per hectare on 0.5+ hectares. Grants include €8,555 per hectare for establishment and €975 per hectare annually for 10 years. Qualifying agroforestry land remains eligible for Basic Income Support for Sustainability (BISS), ensuring CAP Pillar I payments while improving farm sustainability.

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